

10 A SUR INSCRIPTION FROM UDAYAPUR IN MADHYA PRADESH

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The inscription belonging to the time of the Sūr king Islām Shāh is from Udayapūr, a town (23° 54' N ; 78° 6' E) situated in the Bāsoda tahsil of Vidishā district in Madhya Pradesh. It lies about six kilometres from the nearest railway station Bāreth which is on Bhōpāl-Bīna main line of the Central Railway. It is also connected by road with the tahsil and district headquarters which lie towards its south-west respectively at the distance of about 13 kilometres and 55 kilometres.¹

Udayapūr was a town of considerable importance, splendour and architectural grandeur during ancient period as is indicated by the traces of an old stone fortification wall and ruins of ancient temples. The town is said to have been founded by the Paramāra king Udayāditya who ruled over Mālwā from 1059-81 A.D. He also built there the famous temple called after him as Udayēśvara dedicated to god Śiva.²

Udayapūr also appears to have remained a place of sufficient importance during the period of Muslim rule. In the history of Islamic period, we find no reference to it in the chronicles till the reign of Akbar, but we have however an epigraphical evidence from Udayapūr to show that it was occupied by the Tughluqs.³ Udayapūr remained under Muslim occupation

later on of the Mālwā Sulṭān, the Sūrs and the Mughals as is mainly known from the inscriptions found at the place. All these have been listed in the Annual Epigraphical Reports of the Survey and some of them even published in the issues of the departmental journal *Epigraphia Indica-Arabic and Persian Supplement* and other journals.⁴ During the period of the Mughal emperor Akbar, Udayapūr was the *Pargana* headquarters of the Chandēri *Sarkār* in the *Sūba* of Mālwā⁵ and this administrative division continued in the times of Jahāngīr and Shāh Jahān and even upto later Mughals as is indicated by the records of these rulers from the place⁶ and other records.

The epigraph under review is found engraved on a slab measuring 43×63 cm. which is fixed on the central *mihrāb* of a mosque in Paṭhānon-kā-Maḥalla.⁷ The text consists of nine lines of writing in Arabic and Persian prose executed in relief in ordinary Naskh script. The Arabic portion of the text comprising the First Creed, *Bismi'llāh* and the Throne verse of *Qur'ān* occupies the first six lines; while the historical matter in Persian is contained in the following three lines and records that the mosque was constructed in the reign of Islīm Shāh (Islām Shāh) son of Sher Shāh by Khān-i-A'zam Jangī Khān Jhajjū (or Chajjū) during

the governorship of Masnad-i-'Āli Mas'ūd Khān son of Mubārak Chāzī

In the lower border below the Persian text is incised a one line inscription in Sanskrit in *Nāgarī* characters. Though not pro-

perly legible, it contains the name of the architect (*Sūtradhāra*) which reads like Ismāl (i.e. Ismā'il).

The text in Arabic and Persian reads as under :

Text

1. Kalima.
- 2-6 Bismi'llāh and Āyatu'l-Kursī
7. Dar'ahd-i-bandagī Ḥadṛat Islīm Shāh bin Sher Shāh Sulṭān Khallada'llāhu Mulkuhu
8. Kaz'amal-i-bandagī Masnad-i-'Āli Mas'ūd Khān bin Mubārak Ghāzī Wa (rect)in Masjid binā
9. Kard Khān-i-[A]' zam Jangī Khān Jhajjū (or Chajjū) Zi Istiqbāl Shuhūr Sana Sitta (wa) Khāmsīn (wa) tis'amāya māh-i-Ramadān[u'l] Mubārak (?).

Translation

1. First Creed
- 2-6. Bismi'llāh and Throne verse⁹
7. In the reign of His Majesty Ḥadṛat Islīm Shāh son of Sher Shāh Sulṭān, may Allāh perpetuate his kingdom
8. (and) during the administration (i.e. governorship) of the revered Masnad-i-'Āli Mas'ūd Khān son of Mubārak Ghāzī, this mosque was constructed
9. (by) Khān-i-A'zam (i.e. great Khān) Jangī Khān Jhajjū (or Chajjū) in the beginning of the months of the year (A.H.) Six (and) fifty (and) nine-hundred (in the) month of auspicious Ramadān (Ramadān (A.H.) 956=September-October 1549).

As seen above, this epigraph is important in more than one aspect. First it refers to the reign of Islām Shāh who ruled from 1545 to 1554 A.D. So far not many Arabic and Persian inscriptions of the Sūr kings particularly from the Mālṡā region which now formed part of the present Madhya Pradesh have come to light. The province of Mālṡā was brought under the

sway by Sher Shāh in 1542 after defeating Mallū Khān *alias* Qādir Shāh of Māṇḍu and routing Puran Mal of Raisen. Sher Shāh bestowed the whole kingdom of Mālṡā to his general Shujā' at Khān and also appointed *faujḍārs* at different places in the province.¹⁰ Mālṡā continued to be held firmly by his son and successor Islām Shāh who in the later part of his reign made

Gwalior, the permanent capital of his kingdom and began to rule from there until his death in 1554.¹¹

It may not be without interest to note that in this inscription, the name of the king is spelt as Islīm Shāh. This name occurs in a couple of other inscriptions of this ruler.¹² Islām Shāh is variously called as Salīm Shāh, Islām Shāh and Islīm Shāh in the chronicles as well as in the epigraphs.

Secondly the text provides the name of two high officials, namely Khān-i-A'zam Jangī Khān Jhajjū who constructed the mosque and Masnad-i-'Ālī Mas'ūd Khān son of Mubārak Ghāzī during whose governorship the work was carried out. The identification of Mas'ūd Khān and his father Mubārak Ghāzī is difficult to establish with any amount of certainty. We know one Mas'ūd Khān who is found mentioned in the record of Sher Shāh, dated A. H. 947 (1540 A.D.) from Sākit in Uttar Pradesh.¹³ He can not be identified with one under review as the former is mentioned as the son of Mas'ūd Khān, whereas Mas'ūd Khān of our record is the son of Mubārak Ghāzī. Mas'ūd Khān of our record could be identical with another Sūr noble Mas'ūd Khān who alongwith other *amirs* helped prince Ibrāhīm Khān Sūr in his contest for the throne after the death of Islām Shāh.¹⁴ If this identification is correct, the epigraph would provide new information about his later career. In the alternative, Mas'ūd

Khān may be a different official in which case too, the epigraph would be an important document.

As for Mubārak Ghāzī¹⁵ the father of Mas'ūd Khān, his identification is also not established. For want of any further data it is difficult to say if he is identical with Mubārak Khān of Narwar inscriptions dated A.H. 914 (1509 A.D.) of Sikandar Lodī from Madhya Pradesh. He is stated in the records to have been appointed to administer the fort of Narwar after its conquest by the king.¹⁶

Also it has not been possible to trace any reference in the historical works available to me about Khān-i-A'zam Jangī Khān Jhajjū who built the mosque. If the suffix which is read as Jhajjū or Chajjū with his name is indicative of the proper name, it would mean that Jangī Khān may be the title borne by him. That Jangī also held the title Khān-i-A'zam, suggests that he was a distinguished officer. It is likely that he might have held the *Jāgir* of Udayapūr during the period under study.

To sum up, the present inscription constitutes an important source for the history of the Mālvā region of Madhya Pradesh under the Sūr dynasty. It supplies as is clear from its study not only important information in the political field but also indicates on the other hand the building activity during the period.

Notes :-

1 *Madhya Pradesh District Gazetteers* Vidisha (Bhopal, 1979), p. 334.

2 *Ibid.*, p. 334; *Imperial Gazetteer of India*, Vol. XXIV (Oxford, 1908), p. 110; For the

- history of Udayapūr and its monuments see, Cunningham, *Archaeological Survey of India Report*, Vol. VII (Varanasi, 1966), pp. 81-88 ; *Ibid.*, Vol. X, pp. 65-69.
- 3 *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy* 1964-65, Nos., D, 77-78 ; *Indian Antiquary*, Vol. LV (1926), p. 5, pls. I & II.
 - 4 *A.R.Ep.*, 1960-61, Nos. D, 102-11 ; *Ibid.*, 1961-62, Nos. D, 94 ; *Ibid.*, 1964-65, Nos. D, 77-81 ; *Ibid.*, Nos. D, 155-57 ; *Epigraphia Indica-Arabic and Persian Supplement* 1968, pp. 62-64 ; EIAPS., 1969 ; *Indian Ant.*, Vol. LV (1926), p. 5, pl. I & II, *Gwalior Rājya Kē Abhilēkh*, p. 75, No. 564 ; *The Indian Historical Quarterly*, Vol. III, (Reprint, Delhi 1985), pp. 715-18.
 - 5 Abū'l-Fadl, *A'in-i-Akbarī*, Vol. I (Calcutta, 1872), p. 463.
 - 6 *AREp.*, 1960-61, Nos. D, 107-08 ; *Ibid.*, 1965-66, No. D, 155 ; *IHQ*, Vol. III, No. 4, (1927), pp. 715-18.
 - 7 *A.R.Ep.*, 1960-61, No. D, 111.
 - 8 The term is to be taken in its literal meaning, 'months' and not as indicating the *Shuhūr* era.
 - 9 *Qur'ān* Chapter II, verse 255.
 - 10 Sarwānī, *Tārikh-i-Sāhī*, tr. B.P. Ambashthyā (Patna, 1974), pp. 540-545 ; Budāūnī, *Muntakhabu't-Tawārikh*, Vol. I (Calcutta, 1868), pp. 365-67 ; Qānūngo, *Sher Shāh & His times* (N. Delhi, 1965), p. 333 ; *IG*, Vol IX, pp. 338-40.
 - 11 Budaunī, Vol. I, pp. 382, 411-415.
 - 12 *Epigraphia Indo-Moslemica*, 1923.24, p. 28, pl. XIII.
 - 13 *EIAPS*, 1967, p. 39.
 - 14 Budaunī, Vol. I, pp. 423-24.
 - 15 The term *Ghāzī* literary means a participant in a religious war and is normally applied to survivors thereof.
 - 16 *EIAPS*, 1965, pp. 31-33.

PLATE III

A SUR INSCRIPTION, FROM MADHYA PRADESH

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